

EFFECTIVENESS OF LIFE SKILL INTERVENTIONS ON THE QUALITY OF LIFE AMONG PATIENTS WITH ALCOHOL DISORDER

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Introduction: Life skills interventions are crucial for individuals with alcohol use disorders, as they significantly enhance their overall quality of life. These skills not only help individuals navigate daily challenges but are also essential for achieving greater independence. Such interventions address a range of public health concerns, including deteriorating physical health, lack of social support, economic struggles, and overall well-being. By improving psychological, emotional, cognitive, and behavioral abilities, life skills interventions serve as a valuable resource for enhancing quality of life and fostering long-term recovery.

Methods: A qualitative study with a pre-experimental research design was conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of life skills intervention among 60 patients in the de-addiction wards of R.L. Jalappa Hospital and Research Centre. Participants were selected using a non-probability sampling technique and met the specified inclusion criteria. Data were collected using the WHO Quality of Life BREF Questionnaire, and the life skills intervention was administered over a one-month period. A post-test was conducted after the intervention, and the results were analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics.

Results: The mean pretest score for Quality of Life (QoL) was 58 with a standard deviation of 3.4, while the post-test score for patients with alcohol use disorder increased to 107.1 with a standard deviation of 6.6. The obtained t-value of 53.108 was greater than the table value at the 0.05 level of significance, indicating that life skills intervention was effective in significantly improving the quality of life for patients with alcohol use disorder.

Discussion: Life skills interventions have a significant impact on improving the quality of life for patients with alcohol use disorder, particularly in enhancing their ability to manage communication skills, cope with stress, regulate emotions, and develop effective decision-making and problem-solving techniques.

Key terms: *Effectiveness, Life Skill Interventions, Quality of Life.*

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol has been utilized for ages in social, therapeutic, religious, and cultural contexts. The majority of Americans think that adults can drink alcohol responsibly for social and religious purposes. Alcohol abuse, on the other hand, can lead to issues with one's health, relationships, finances, and legal standing¹. People utilize it to celebrate, mingle, unwind, and improve meal satisfaction². Alcoholism, roughly speaking, is any alcohol consumption that causes serious issues with mental or physical health³. Alcoholism is not a recognized diagnostic entity since there is controversy over what it means, and because the term has negative connotations, its use is discouraged^{4,5}.

According to the National Family Health Survey-5 (NFHS-5), 2019–21, alcohol consumption is higher among men and women in rural India than in urban India. In average, 1% of women who are 15 or older and 19% of men in the same age range use alcohol. Among women, this breaks down to 1.6% (rural) and 0.6% (urban), although for men, it is 19.9% and 16.5%, respectively⁶. One in ten to one in five drinkers eventually develops alcoholism and alcohol dependence. Age, education, Level of intelligence, or socioeconomic level are not factors in who develops alcoholism; it can develop to anyone. According to studies, India might be the third-largest global market for alcoholic beverages⁷.

The World Health Organization defines quality of life (QoL) as "an individual's perception of their position in life within the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards, and concerns". Wealth, work, the environment, physical and mental health, education, leisure activities, social connections, religious beliefs, safety, security, and freedom are all common measures of life quality⁸. Recent research have tried to re-frame quality of life (QoL) into distinct categories because it has been acknowledged that it is difficult to arrive at a widely accepted definition and assessment⁹.

QoL is a crucial measure that sheds light on how a disorder affects the lives of persons who are affected⁸. Patients with the chronic alcohol use disorder must mobilise all of their capacities for adaptation and reconstruction. A useful indicator to assess the patient's subjective experience and to calculate the psychosocial burden of alcoholism is quality of life (QoL), which is a term that sits in between social and clinical sciences. Since good treatment should not only improve the clinical state and prognosis of the patient, but also their QoL, patient-reported outcome measures like QoL may be helpful in guiding decision between various therapeutic alternatives. Despite

being important to the psychosocial context of therapies, the QoL of alcohol-dependent patients is not routinely assessed in current practice. Studies on individuals with alcoholism have indicated that their quality of life has significantly diminished, but there is little data on how QoL changes as a result of therapeutic interventions. Although several studies had noted a poor quality of life (QoL) in alcohol-dependent patients at the start of therapy, the causes had not been systematically investigated¹⁰.

The UNICEF Evaluation Office asserts that "there is no definitive list" of psychosocial skills, but UNICEF identifies psychosocial and interpersonal skills as being equally important to reading and numeracy abilities and generally focused on well-being. It is regarded as a notion with an elastic nature because its meaning varies from culture to culture and depending on one's life circumstances¹¹.

Financial literacy can differ from life skills. The following core cross-cultural life skill areas were identified by the World Health Organization in 1999: decision-making and problem-solving; creative and critical thinking; communication and interpersonal skills; self-awareness and empathy; assertiveness and equanimity; and resilience and coping with emotions and stress with yoga and meditation. The goal of life skills training is to change a person's expected or projected trajectory of development through a people-centered approach and planned programming. Intervention programme such as establishing a health policy and creating a pleasant school climate, therefore have significant effects on student outcomes. As a result, it offers solid support for the possibility of interventions¹².

Social skills and social support Reduced vulnerability to stress, depression, physical illness, and unhealthy lifestyle choices like drinking alcohol, smoking cigarettes, and using marijuana will also help kids resist peer pressure to engage in risky behaviors like drug use and early.¹³

In the view of the above information and the investigators experience of working among alcohol dependents in selected psychiatric ward Kolar, the investigators found that there is decreased Quality of Life among the alcohol dependence patients. Hence the investigator wants to estimate the Quality of Life by using the WHO Quality of Life.

Studies related to intervention and outcome on alcohol Addicted individuals

An experimental study on the subject to assess effectiveness of motivational interviewing for substance use was done by Geirsmeslund, Rigmor C Berg in India. Randomized controlled trial method was adopted in the selection of 13,342 participants and assessed the motivational interviewing (MI) for substance abuse. The result pageant that there was no significant difference between MI and treatment as usual for either follow up post intervention and medium follow up. The findings from this study advocate that MI can reduce the extent of substance abuse compared to no interview.¹⁸

An experimental study was conducted on the topic Internal medicine residency training for unhealthy alcohol and other drug use by Angela H Jackson, in his research article explained the development of unhealthy substance use related competencies, and described a curriculum in unhealthy substance use that integrates these competencies into internal medicine resident physician training. He outlined strategies to facilitate adoption of such curricula by the residency programs. This provides an outline for the actual implementation of the curriculum within the structure of a training program, with examples using common teaching venues. He described and linked the content to the core competencies mandated by the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education, the formal accrediting body for residency training programs in the United States. Specific topics are recommended, with suggestions on how to integrate such teaching into existing internal medicine residency training program curricula. To conclude, given the burden of disease and effective interventions available that can be delivered by internal medicine physicians, teaching about unhealthy substance use must be incorporated into internal medicine residency training, and can be done within existing teaching venues.¹⁹

A quasi-experimental study was conducted by Charles Alan Walker he focused study on alcohol addiction combined twelve step approach in conjunction with Buddhist philosophies, complementary therapies, or both. The subject requirements were a minimum of five years of continuous sobriety, possession of at least a bachelor's degree, as well as no physical or sexual abuse experienced in the family of origin. The researcher utilized an ad hoc meaning generation approach for interpreting each subject's interview responses. Results supported the hypothesis that Buddhist philosophies and complementary therapies can be utilized to effectively support and enhance recovery. The subjects reported that the programs provided a culture of support for their recovery by attending meetings, working the Twelve Steps with a sponsor, as well as

providing a spiritual path for living life sober. The author concluded that Buddhist philosophies enhanced their Twelve Step recovery by teaching nonattachment to ego, focus, and awareness through meditation, as well as connection with a collective spirituality and complementary therapies enhanced their Twelve Step recovery by providing various methodologies to reduce cravings, enhance detoxification, as well as provided ongoing practices to enhance their physical and spiritual connection.²⁰

An experimental study was conducted on the topic effect of preventive intervention on underage drinkers by Toomey in United State (n=785). His intervention model was implemented on adolescents' families that include life skill training and alternative activities. The results showed significant effect and author concluded that life skill training and activities as effective preventive measures in reduction of alcohol abuse.²¹

An experimental study was conducted to determine the effect of continued care on subjects with alcohol dependence by Pratima Murthy at Bangalore state of India. The study participants were split into control group and experimental group and were classed on the Alcohol Problem Questionnaire. This study was conducted among 99 patients consisted of 48 males and 2 females in the de-addiction service of National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences at Bangalore in India. The study showed statistically advancement in the area of marital and employment problems ($p < 0.05$) and in areas of problem with children ($p < 0.01$). the study findings advocate that the sustaining effect of continued care will have direct effect on alcohol dependence.²²

A meta- analytic study was conducted on the topic efficacy of motivational interviewing as a brief intervention for excessive drinking by Cox Miles to examined whether or not motivational interviewing is more efficacies than no intervention in reducing alcohol consumption. A literature search followed especially a Meta analytic review of randomized control trials revealed efficacy of brief Motivational Interview with aggregate effect size of 0.43. (95% CL) and permitted especially MI's long term efficacy effectiveness.²³

Studies related to life skill intervention among alcohol dependent patients

A quasi-experimental study on the topic effectiveness of a life skill intervention to change the attitudes of youth towards alcohol and drug abuse by Jagpreet Kaur, V P Joshit at Punjab state of

India. Likert scale is used for measuring the attitudes of college students towards alcohol and drug abuse were developed for the purpose of this study. This study conduct among a sample of 1000 first Year College students from six randomly selected district of Punjab, India. The F-values for the main effect of the life skill intervention on mean attitude score with regard to alcohol and drug abuse were 356.24 and 444.59 respectively ($p < 0.01$). The findings from this study suggests that the introduction of appropriate life skill programs within institute of higher education in India, could significantly improves the attitudes of youngsters towards the misuse of illicit drugs.²⁴

An experimental study was conducted with the aim of assessing the impact of life skill training on promotion of drug abuse preventive behavior by Mahdi Moskhi, TahereHassanzade at Gonabad Medical University. This study conducted among 60 students in Gonabad Medical University. The samples were selected through quota random sampling and assigned randomly into 2 intervention and control groups. Data were collected through questionnaire, including 2 sections of demographic information and drug abuse preventive behaviors. The result showed a significant difference in the comparison of post-test mean scores ($P < 0.01$) which remained stable 4 years after intervention. There was a significant relationship between father's educational level and drug abuse preventive behaviors ($P < 0.01$). This study evidenced life skill training is effective in the promotion of drug abuse preventive behavior of university students.²⁵

A quasi-experimental study was performed on the topic Alcoholics anonymous and 12 step facilitation treatment for alcohol use disorder by John F Kelly and Maricaferri through six bibliographic database. Randomized controlled trial was adopted in the selection of 10,565 study participants. Participants were male and female over 18 years old with AUD. The result showed that there was an advantage for more intensive 12 step treatment ($p = 0.01$). The findings from this study propose AA/TSF interventions produce similar benefits to other treatment on all drinking related outcomes.²⁶

Studies Related to Quality of Life Among Alcohol Dependent Patients

An experimental study was conducted to examine the prospective changes in Quality of life among alcohol dependence patient by Shruti Srivastava and Manjeet S. Bhatia at De- addiction Outpatient clinic of University College of Medical Sciences and Guru Teg Bahadur Hospital in Delhi. This study conducted in 56 patients of age from 18-45 years of alcohol dependence over a three months period. Data were collected through answering questionnaires, undergoing

laboratory investigations, attending group sections. The results indicated no correlation between the severity of alcohol dependence scores and domain scores of Who QoL-BREF, physical domain: $r = -0.17$, $P = 0.2$, Psychological domain: $r = -0.19$, $P = 0.14$, social domain: $r = 0.04$, $P = 0.75$, environmental domain: $r = 0.4$, $P = 0.77$. The study confirms poor quality of life in patients in alcohol dependence before interventions. The regular follow up with the family members in outpatient settings enables the patient to achieve complete abstinence, thereby improving their quality of life.²⁷

An experimental study conducted to investigate Quality of life and its correlates in Alcohol Use Disorder patients with or without depression in China by Hui Huang, Kui Ning. The study conducted among five hundred and fifteen psychiatric patients diagnosed with AUD. A self-developed questionnaire is used to assess 515 patients for demographic characteristics, drinking pattern, comorbid disorder, drinking related treatments and patients attitudes and expectations for treatment. The self-developed questionnaire and structured interview on AUD were administered by trained and experienced psychiatrist. The result compared with AUD patients without depression, those with depression had a lower quality of life. In all eight domains of the SF-36 (all $P < 0.001$), but were more willing to have alcohol related treatment ($P < 0.05$). The findings shows that early interventions in comorbid depression will help to improve quality of life.²⁸

A community based cross sectional study was conducted by Jeby Jose Olickal, Ganesh Kumar Saya to assess the independent association of alcohol use with Quality of Life in Puducherry, South India. The study conducted among 316 adult men aged above 18 years in Puducherry, South India. Individuals selected using multistage sampling techniques besides, the data were collected through WHO QoL BREF questionnaire. Results showed high risk alcohol users and urban residence had 11.2 and 4.1 less QoL scores respectively and educated had 7 more QoL scores compared to the reference category. The findings shows that alcohol use is correlated with low quality of life and there is a need of alcohol de-addiction strategies to reduce alcohol use and improve their QoL.²⁹

Studies Related to Life Skill Intervention in Improving The Quality Of Life Among the Alcohol Dependent Patients.

A predictive study conducted by Kishore Kumar Rai, Vandana to assess the role of life skills and attitude towards alcohol abusing predicting academic achievement of school students of Sikkim, a North -eastern state of India. The study conducted among a total number of 726 class 11

students were selected from the schools of Sikkim, India, using stratified random sampling technique. Data were analysed using life skill assessment scale to assess the life skills of students. The results shows that life skills and attitudes towards alcohol abuse significantly predict student's academic achievements. 15.3% variance in academic achievements of students was explained by life skills and attitude towards alcohol abuse ($R=0.391$, $P=0.000$), Further, the t- test result reflects that both the variables had significant predictive power to predict student's academic achievements. The findings shows that there was a significant relationship between academic achievement and life skills and attitude towards alcohol abuse of school students.³⁰

A quasi-experimental study was conducted by Roshni, Rohit Kumar Turi about the application of quality of life, problem solving skills and treatment motivation through motivational enhancement therapy among individuals with alcohol dependence from Dewada, Rajnandgoan, India. The sample consists of a total of 10 patients were diagnosed with alcohol dependence using a purposive sampling selected from the outpatient department of the CIIMHANS, Dewada, Rajnandgoan, India. The data were collected through questionnaire by dividing the patients into two groups as experimental group and control group. The result revealed that the experimental group of alcohol dependence patients improved in different domains of problem solving and coping skills as compared to control group.³¹

A quasi-experimental study was conducted by HananAbdElwahabEi Sayed, HedyafathyMohy to evaluate the effect of life skill intervention on social; self-efficacy for prevention of drug abuse among young adolescents student at Benha city, Egypt. The study conducted among 120 students at two preparatory school in Benha city. The students were selected through simple random sampling method and two tools were used for data collection; first tool children's self- efficacy in peer interactions and life skill training questionnaire respectively. The result shows a significant improvement ($P<0.05$) regarding to student's social self-efficacy in conflict and non - conflict situation, life skill knowledge and anti-smoking knowledge, anti -drinking and anti-smoking attitudes and life skills behaviors after the life skill intervention as compared to before.³²

METHODOLOGY

RESEARCH APPROACH

A quantitative study with evaluative research approach is considered as appropriate for the study.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design selected for the present study is pre-experimental research design (one group pre-test post-test design).

VARIABLES UNDER STUDY:

- **Independent variable:** Life Skill Intervention
- **Dependent variable:** Quality of Life.
- **Extraneous Variables:** Age, Marital status, education, occupation, religion, income, family type, number of Children, sources of information about de-addiction, reason for first drink, the amount of alcohol which the individual consumes per drink.

SETTING

The study was conducted in R.L.Jalappa Hospital and Research Centre-Psychiatric de-addiction ward with 40 beds at Kolar.

POPULATION

Patients with Alcohol Disorder admitted in R.L.Jalappa Hospital and Research Centre-Psychiatric de-addiction ward.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLE SIZE

The sample for this study consists of approximately 60Patients with Alcohol Disorder who are diagnosed with alcohol dependence.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Non-probability Convenient sampling technique.

SAMPLING CRITERIA

Inclusion criteria

1. Subjects who met ICD-10 criteria for Alcohol dependence
2. Subjects who are able to read and understand Kannada/English
3. Subjects whose cognitive function is adequate (MMSE score above 25)
4. Patients with Alcohol Disorder who are admitted in De-addiction ward at the time of data collection.

Exclusion criteria

1. Subjects who are reluctant to participate in this study.
2. Individuals suffering from other co-morbid illness.
3. Individuals with the diagnosis of multiple substance use.
4. Subjects who have undergone life skill intervention.

HYPOTHESES

H₁: There will be statistically significant difference between mean pre-test scores and post test scores of quality of life among Patients with Alcohol Disorder through life skill intervention.

H₂: there will be statistically significant association between post test scores of quality of life among Patients with Alcohol Disorder with selected socio-demographic variables.

DATA COLLECTION TOOL

It consists of 3 sections:

Section A: Socio-demographic profile:

It includes question regarding the personal details of the people such as Age, Marital status, education, occupation, religion, income, family type, number of Children, sources of information about de-addiction, reason for first drink, the amount of alcohol which the individual consumes per drink, Family history of alcohol consumption.

Section B: WHO, Quality of Life (QOL) Scale.

It is a standardized scale, consists of 26 items to assess the Quality of Life among the patients with alcohol disorder.

The WHOQOL-100 quality of life assessment was developed by the WHOQOL group with fifteen international field centers, simultaneously, in an attempt to develop a quality of life assessment that applicable cross- culturally.

Q1-Below 2 poor QOL

2-3 Average (neither poor nor good)

3-4 Good QOL

4-5 Very good QOL

Q2-Below 2 Poor General health

2-3 Average (neither poor nor good)

3-4 Good general health

4-5 Very good general health

Domain 1=Range 7-35(7 items)

Below 14 Poor Physical Health

14-21 Average (neither poor nor good)

21-28 Good Physical Health

28-35 Very Good Physical Health

Domain 2=Range 6-30(6 items)

Below 12 Poor Psychological Health

12-18 Average (neither poor nor good)

18-24 Good Psychological Health

24-30 Very Good Psychological Health

Domain 3=Range 3-15(3 items)

Below 6 Poor Social Relationship

6-9 Average (neither poor nor good)

9-12 good social relationship

12-15 very good relationship

Domain 4=Range 16-40(8 items)

Below 16 Poor Environment

16-24 Average (neither poor nor good) Environmental Safety

24-32 Good Environmental Safety

32-40 Very good environmental safety

Section C: Life skill Intervention among patients with alcohol disorder which includes 10 life skill intervention (self-awareness, Empathy, coping with stress, Coping with Emotions, Communication skills, Interpersonal relationship, Creative thinking, Critical thinking, Problem solving and Decision making) along with Yoga & Meditation.

DAY	Duration	Activity	LIFE SKILL INTERVENTION	OBJECTIVES
Day 1	2hrs	Johari window model-with yoga & Exercise	Self-awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To know about themselves To improve awareness self-awareness of patients.
Day 2	2hrs	Blind fold, Life Turning points-with yoga & Exercise	Coping with stress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To reduce their stress level. To improve the coping skills.
Day 3	2hrs	Making charts on how to cope up with stressors-with yoga & Exercise	Empathy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To develop an empathetic response. To understand human needs. To understand others perspective.
Day 4	2hrs	Balloon blasting-with yoga & Exercise	Good communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To know about the importance of communication. To improve the communication skills. To learn how to a good communicator.
Day 5	2hrs	Forming the mirror image- with yoga& Exercise	Creative thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To overcome blocks to creativity. To improve the thinking skills. To discover the creative ability.
Day 6	2hrs	Group interaction with life turning points- with yoga & Exercise	Decisions making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To improve the decision-making skills. To know the importance of decision making. To improve the quality of decision.
Day 7	2hrs	Creative art by the patients with- yoga & Exercise	Critical thinking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To understand what is thinking skill. To improve thinking capacity. To encourage to solve the problems.
Day 8	2hrs	Storytelling and rope making with- yoga & Exercise	Problem solving	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To solve problem by applying problem solving process. To derive or design solution for problem. To implement the solution.
Day 9	2hrs	Situation choosing and making solution with- yoga & Exercise	Interpersonal relationship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To improve the interpersonal relationship. To state the essential of interpersonal relationship. To develop and maintain positive feeling.
Day	2hrs	Marbles counting	Coping with stress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To understand our own feelings. To respect others emotions or

10		with- yoga & Exercise		feelings. • To identify the way to control or reduce emotions.
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Validity of the Content:

Validity is the degree to which an instrument measures has an appropriate sample of items for the construct being measured and adequately covers the construct domain. Content validity is relevant for both affective and cognitive measures.

The selected tool along with the objectives, questionnaire was send to 05 experts for authorizing content validity and was validated by 05 experts.

METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION

Step-I

1. The permission was obtained from Institutional ethics committee of Sri DevarajUrs College of nursing, Kolar and concerned hospital authorities of R.L.Jalappa Hospital & Research Centre, Tamaka, Kolar.

Step-II

1. The study subjects was selected by using convenient sampling technique who fulfils the inclusion criteria.
2. Prior to the data collection the investigator was familiarized with the study subjects and explain the purpose of study to them.
3. The investigator was requested the participants for their full co-operation and assure them the confidentiality of their response.
4. Written informed consent was obtained from the study subjects.
5. The duration of the study was approximately three month/ until the desired sample obtains.

Step-III

1. Pre-test was conducted by using WHO, Quality of Life (QOL) Scale.
2. Followed by the pre-test Life Skill Intervention (10skills) was given for Patients with Alcohol Disorder who fulfils the inclusion criteria for one month to improve the quality of life.

Life Skill Intervention Schedule

Sl. No	Day	Duration	Life skill Intervention	Activity	The activities will be continued for 20 days and 30 th day the post test will be conducted by using same pre-test Questionnaire for the patients with Alcohol disorders .
1.	Day-1	2hrs	Self-awareness	Day-1: Pre-test Johari window model-with yoga & Exercise	
2.	Day-2	2hrs	Empathy	Blind fold, Life Turning points-with yoga & Exercise	
3.	Day-3	2hrs	Coping with stress	Making charts on how to cope up with stressors-with yoga & Exercise	
4.	Day-4	2hrs	Coping with Emotions	Balloon blasting-with yoga & Exercise	
5.	Day-5	2hrs	Communication skills	Forming the mirror image- with yoga & Exercise	
6.	Day-6	2hrs	Interpersonal relationship	Group interaction with life turning points-with yoga & Exercise	
7.	Day-7	2hrs	Creative thinking	Creative art by the patients with- yoga & Exercise	
8.	Day-8	2hrs	Critical thinking	Storytelling and rope making with- yoga & Exercise	
9.	Day-9	2hrs	Problem solving	Situation choosing and making solution with- yoga & Exercise	
10.	Day-10	2hrs	Decision making	Marbles counting with- yoga & Exercise	

3. Post-test was conducted by using same pre-test Questionnaire.

PLAN FOR DATA ANALYSIS

Data was analyzed by using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics.

- Frequency and percentage distribution for socio-demographic variables
- Quality of life was analyzed by comparing pre and post test scores among Patients with Alcohol Disorder by paired t test.
- Chi-square test was used for association between Quality of life among Patients with Alcohol Disorder with the selected sociodemographic variables.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

Ethical clearance was granted from the institution ethical committee, Sri Devaraj Urs College of Nursing and to conduct the study permission has got from medical superintendent, R.L. Jalappa Hospital and Research Centre. Information was taken from study participants before collecting the data.

Life skill Intervention among patients with alcohol disorder which includes 10 life skill intervention (self-awareness, Empathy, coping with stress, Coping with Emotions, Communication skills, Interpersonal relationship, Creative thinking, Critical thinking, Problem solving and Decision making) along with Yoga & Meditation.

Day	Duration	Activity	Intervention	Objectives
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Day 9	2hrs	Situation choosing and making solution with- yoga & Exercise	Interpersonal relationship	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To improve the interpersonal relationship. To state the essential of interpersonal relationship. To develop and maintain positive feeling.
Day 10	2hrs	Marbles counting with- yoga & Exercise	Coping with stress	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To understand our own feelings. To respect others emotions or feelings. To identify the way to control or reduce emotions.

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of socio demographic variables of patients with alcohol disorder
N=60

SI. No	Socio-demographic variables	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1.	Age a) 15-25 b) 26-35 c) 35 above	16 22 22	26.66 36.67 36.67
2.	Marital status a) Married b) Unmarried c) Divorced d) Widower	40 15 5 00	66.67 25 8.33 00
3.	Educational status a) Illiterate b) Primary school c) High school d) Secondary school e) UG f) PG	00 25 14 11 00 10	00 41.67 23.33 18.33 00 17
4.	Occupation a) Not working b) Government job c) Private job d) Business	15 10 16 19	25 16.67 26.67 31.67
5.	Religion a) Hindu b) Muslim c) Christian d) Others	59 01 00 00	98.33 1.67 00 00
6.	Family history of alcohol consumption a) Yes b) No	36 24	60 40
7.	Monthly income a) <10000 b) 10000-20000 c) >20000	24 30 6	40 50 10
8.	Type of family a) Nuclear family b) Joint family	22 38	36.67 63.33
9.	No. of Children a) One b) Two c) More than two	13 38 09	21.67 63.33 15
10.	Source of information about deaddiction a) Friends b) Family members c) Median d) Others	36 17 07 00	60 28.33 11.67 00

11.	Reason for first alcohol consumption a) Peer pressure b) Family problems c) Occupational environment d) Social gathering	33 18 09 00	55 30 15 00
12.	Have you undergone life skill interventions in life time a) Yes b) No	3 57	5 95

Table 2: Description of assessment of domain wise pretest mean scores of quality of Life among patient with Alcohol Disorder by using WHO, QOL Scale.

N=60

Variables	Below Average		Above Average	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Quality of life	17.5	10.6	12.5	17.67
General health	16	14.14	14	19.79
Physical health	28	38.18	2	2.82
Psychological health	28.5	38.89	1.5	2.12
Social relationship	30	39.59	0	0
Environmental safety	30	16.97	0	0

Table 3: Description of assessment of domain wise posttest mean scores of quality of Life among patient with Alcohol Disorder by using WHO, QOL Scale.

N=60

Variables	Below Average		Above Average	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
Quality of life	2.5	0.70	27.5	3.5
General health	3.5	0.70	26.5	9.19
Physical health	3.5	0.70	26.5	16.26
Psychological health	1.5	0.70	28.5	20.50
Social relationship	02	00	28	25.45
Environmental safety	1.5	0.70	28.5	33.23

Table 4: Comparison of quality of life between pretest and posttest mean scores.

Variables	Mean	SD	t value	p value
Pre test	58	3.4	53.108	0.0004
Post test	107.1	6.6		SS

P < 0.05 at 59 df

SS- Statistically significant

Table 5: Association between Posttest Quality of Life score with selected demographic variables among patients with Alcohol Disorder. N=60

SI No.	Demographic Variables	Quality of life		X ² calculated value	DF	p value	Inference
		Below average	Above average				
1.	Age in years 15-35 years More than 35	2	25	0.0551	1	0.81	P at 0.05 NS
		3	30				
2.	Educational status Illiterate Literate	3	15	2.3377	1	0.13	P at 0.05 NS
		2	40				
3.	Occupation Job Jobless	1	30	2.1903	1	0.14	P at 0.05 NS
		4	25				
4.	Religion Hindu Others	4	50	0.6061	1	0.44	P at 0.05 NS
		1	5				
5.	Family history of alcohol consumption Yes No	3	35	0.0261	1	0.87	P at 0.05 NS
		2	20				
6.	Monthly income 10,000-20,000 >20,000	1	30	2.1903	1	0.14	P at 0.05 NS
		4	25				
7.	Types of family Nuclear Joint	3	45	1.3636	1	0.24	P at 0.05 NS
		2	10				
8.	No. of children One- two More than two	1	40	5.8887	1	0.01	P at 0.05 SS
		4	15				
9.	Have you undergone						

	life skill intervention in your life						
	Yes	1	2				P at 0.05
	No	4	53	2.5837	1	0.10	NS

Table 6: Association between Posttest General Health score with selected demographic variables among patients with Alcohol Disorder. N=60

SI No.	Demographic Variables	Quality of life		X ² calculated value	DF	p value	Inference
		Below average	Above average				
1.	Age in years			0.0686	1	0.79	P at 0.05 NS
	15-35 years	3	20				
	More than 35	4	33				
2.	Educational status			0.0539	1	0.82	P at 0.05 NS
	Illiterate	2	13				
	Literate	5	40				
3.	Occupation			0.0686	1	0.79	P at 0.05 NS
	Job	4	33				
	Jobless	3	20				
4.	Religion			0.5548	1	0.46	P at 0.05 NS
	Hindu	5	44				
	Others	2	9				
5.	Family history of alcohol consumption			0.4852	1	0.49	P at 0.05 NS
	Yes	6	39				
	No	1	14				
6.	Monthly income			3.1832	1	0.07	P at 0.05 NS
	10,000-20,000	4	45				
	>20,000	3	8				
7.	Types of family			6.4767	1	0.01	P at 0.05 SS
	Nuclear	2	40				
	Joint	5	13				
8.	No. of children			0.0539	1	0.82	P at 0.05 NS
	One- two	5	40				
	More than two	2	13				

9.	Have you undergone life skill intervention in your life						
	Yes	1	3	0.7393	1	0.39	P at 0.05 NS
	No	6	50				

Table7: Association between Posttest Physical Health score with selected demographic variables among patients with Alcohol Disorder.

N=60

SI No.	Demographic Variables	Quality of life		X ² calculated value	DF	p value	Inference
		Below average	Above average				
1.	Age in years 15-35 years More than 35	3	15	0.6238	1	0.43	P at 0.05 NS
		4	38				
2.	Educational status Illiterate Literate	4	10	5.0637	1	0.02	P at 0.05 SS
		3	43				
3.	Occupation Job Jobless	5	17	4.1236	1	0.04	P at 0.05 SS
		2	36				
4.	Religion Hindu Others	6	47	0.0527	1	0.82	P at 0.05 NS
		1	6				
5.	Family history of alcohol consumption Yes No	3	41	3.7638	1	0.05	P at 0.05 NS
		4	12				
6.	Monthly income 10,000-20,000 >20,000	2	39	5.7899	1	0.02	P at 0.05 SS
		5	14				
7.	Types of family Nuclear Joint	3	45	6.8229	1	0.008	P at 0.05 SS
		4	8				
8.	No. of children One- two More than two	2	50	23.1453	1	0.00001	P at 0.05 SS
		5	3				
9.	Have you undergone life skill intervention in your life Yes No	2	1	9.2694	1	0.002	P at 0.05 SS
		5	52				

Table 8: Association between Posttest Psychological Health score with selected demographic variables among patients with Alcohol Disorder.**N=60**

SI No.	Demographic Variables	Quality of life		X ² calculated value	DF	p value	Inference
		Below average	Above average				
1.	Age in years 15-35 years More than 35	2	43	0.117	1	0.73	P at 0.05 NS
		1	14				
2.	Educational status Illiterate Literate	1	52	9.2694	1	0.002	P at 0.05 SS
		2	5				
3.	Occupation Job Jobless	2	49	0.8325	1	0.36	P at 0.05 NS
		1	8				
4.	Religion Hindu Others	2	52	1.9103	1	0.16	P at 0.05 NS
		1	5				
5.	Family history of alcohol consumption Yes No	2	29	0.2845	1	0.59	P at 0.05 NS
		1	28				
6.	Monthly income 10,000-20,000 >20,000	1	35	0.9353	1	0.33	P at 0.05 NS
		2	22				
7.	Types of family Nuclear Joint	2	13	2.924	1	0.08	P at 0.05 NS
		1	44				
8.	No. of children One- two More than two	1	38	1.3919	1	0.24	P at 0.05 NS
		2	19				
9.	Have you undergone life skill intervention in your life Yes No	1	2	5.327	1	0.02	P at 0.05 SS
		2	55				

Table 9: Association between Posttest Social Relationship score with selected demographic variables among patients with Alcohol Disorder.

N=60

SI No.	Demographic Variables	Quality of life		X ² calculated value	DF	p value	Inference
		Below average	Above average				
1.	Age in years 15-35 years More than 35	2	46	2.4107	1	0.12	P at 0.05 NS
		2	10				
2.	Educational status Illiterate Literate	1	6	0.7393	1	0.39	P at 0.05 NS
		3	50				
3.	Occupation Job Jobless	3	43	0.0067	1	0.93	P at 0.05 NS
		1	13				
4.	Religion Hindu Others	2	52	7.619	1	0.005	P at 0.05 SS
		2	4				
5.	Family history of alcohol consumption Yes No	3	43	0.0067	1	0.93	P at 0.05 NS
		1	13				
6.	Monthly income 10,000-20,000 >20,000	1	40	3.7191	1	0.54	P at 0.05 NS
		3	16				
7.	Types of family Nuclear Joint	3	49	0.5048	1	0.48	P at 0.05 NS
		1	7				
8.	No. of children One- two More than two	3	48	0.3361	1	0.56	P at 0.05 NS
		1	8				
9.	Have you undergone life skill intervention in your life Yes No	2	5	6.1109	1	0.01	P at 0.05 SS
		2	51				

Conclusion

- The domain pre-test mean score of quality of life among alcohol disorder patients is less than the domain post-test mean score of quality of life among alcohol disorder patients.
- The computed t test ($t_{59}=53.108$) indicated there is a significant difference between pre and post-test quality of life among patients with alcohol disorder.
- There will be a significant association between quality of life with selected demographic variable like a number of children among patients with alcohol disorder.
- There will be a significant association between general health with selected demographic variables like type of family among patients with alcohol disorder.
- There will be a significant association between the physical health with selected demographic variables like educational status, occupation, monthly income, types of family, no of children, and past experience of any life skill intervention.
- There will be a significant association between the psychological health with selected demographic variables like educational status and past experiences of any life skill intervention.
- There will be a significant association between the social relationship with selected demographic variable like religion and past experience of any life skill intervention.
- There will be a significant association between environmental safety with the selected demographic variable like age in years.

DISCUSSION

Assessment of domain wise pretest and posttest mean score of quality of life among patients with alcohol disorder by using WHO, QOL scale.

The findings of the study (Table 2 and figure 1) disclosed the mean score of pretest quality of life among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $17.5 \pm SD 10.6$ and above average $12.5 \pm SD 17.67$ and perceived general health of mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $16 \pm SD 14.14$ and above average $14 \pm SD 19.79$. The physical health mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $28 \pm SD 38.18$ and above average $2 \pm SD 2.82$. In addition psychological health of mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $28.5 \pm SD 38.89$ and above average $1.5 \pm SD 2.12$. Social relationship of mean score among alcohol disorder patient was below average $30 \pm SD 39.59$ and above average $0 \pm$

SD 0. Besides, environmental safety mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $30 \pm \text{SD } 16.97$ and above average $0 \pm \text{SD } 0$.

The findings of the study (Table 3 and figure 3) disclosed the mean score of post-test quality of life among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $2.5 \pm \text{SD } 0.70$ and above average $27.5 \pm \text{SD } 3.5$ and perceived general health of mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $3.5 \pm \text{SD } 0.70$ and above average $26.5 \pm \text{SD } 9.19$. The physical health mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $3.5 \pm \text{SD } 0.70$ and above average $26.5 \pm \text{SD } 16.26$. Furthermore, psychological health of mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $1.5 \pm \text{SD } 0.70$ and above average $28.5 \pm \text{SD } 20.50$. Social relationship of mean score among alcohol disorder patient was below average $2 \pm \text{SD } 0$ and above average $28 \pm \text{SD } 25.45$. Besides, environmental safety mean score among alcohol disorder patient was with below average $1.5 \pm \text{SD } 0.70$ and above average $28.5 \pm \text{SD } 33.23$.

3. Comparison of pre and posttest mean scores of quality of life for evaluating the effectiveness among patient with alcohol disorder.

The findings of the study (table 4) affirmed that the pretest mean score of quality of life among patients with alcohol disorder that is 58 with SD 3.4 is lesser than the posttest mean score of quality of life among patients with alcoholic disorder that is 107.1 with SD 6.6. The attained t value 53.108 was higher than the table value at 0.05 level significance at 59 df. Hence the hypothesis H_1 is achieved.

Study findings are endorsed by a cross-sectional study to assess whether agnized the quality of life in patient with alcohol use disorders admitted to de addiction centers by using WHOQOL-BREF scale. Patients admitted in de-addiction centers were screened for alcoholism using WHOQOL-BREF questionnaire. Result this study showed that the domain mean score were between 50 and 60 on the 0-100 scale. The selected demographic variables such as age, social class, residential area, marital status and years of drinking were endowed to be significantly accompliced with the domain score.³⁴

1. Association between post-test quality of life scores with selected demographic variables among patients with alcohol disorder.

Chi square tables value shows that there was significant association between posttest quality of life among patient with alcohol disorder with selected demographic variable such as age,

educational status, occupation, religion, family history of alcohol consumption, monthly income, type of family, number of children and any previous experience of life skill intervention. Compared to other domains of quality-of-life physical domain had the highest significant value, since the calculated chi square value was lesser than the table value 3.84 at 0.05 level of significance. Hence the hypothesis H_2 was credited.

Study findings are supported by a community based cross sectional analytic study was conducted among adult men aged above 18 years in field practice areas of a tertiary care medical institution in Puducherry. A total number of 316 participant were confined in the study. In this study a validated pretested Tamil version of World Health Organization's Alcohol Use Disorder Identification (WHO – AUDIT) questioner was used to assess alcohol used and WHO QoL BREF questioners was used to assess the QoL. The result of the study laid out that over all mean score of quality of life was lower among alcohol uses compare to non-alcohol uses, and was found to be statistically significant (P value <0.001).²⁹

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Bethesda. Information about alcohol. Biological Sciences Curriculum Study.NIH Curriculum Supplement Series [online] National Institutes of Health [(2007),(cited on 2023 Dec 15)]. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK20360/>.
2. Rockville MD. Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality. National survey of drug use and health [(2015), (cited on 2023 Dec 16)].
3. Littrell J, Hoboken, Taylor and Fransis. Understanding and Treating alcoholism. An empirically bases clinician's hand book for treatment of alcohol Vol 1. Biological, psychological and social aspects of alcohol consumption and abuse Vol 2; [(2014), (2017 Jul 12), (cited on Dec 17)]; 55
4. Morris J, Moss A, C Albery. The alcoholic other harmful drinkers resist problem recognition to manage identity threat" addictive behaviors.[online] [(2022 Jan 1)(cited on 2023 Dec 19)].
5. Ashford, Robert D, Brenda. Substance use recovery and linguistics the impact of word choice on explicit and implicit bias. *Drug and Alcohol Dependence*. 189 [(cited on Dec 19)] 131–138.
6. <https://indianexpress.com/article/explained/alcohol-consumption-in-india-trends-across-states-age-groups-7920871/>
7. Dr. SrikalaBharat, Dr. K.V. Kishore Kumar. Empowering Adolescents with Life Skills for Psychosocial Competence. Department of psychiatry National Institute of Mental Health and Neuroscience, First edition;[(2014),(cited on 2023 Dec 20)].
8. Martha Nussbaum, Amartya Sen. QOL has a wide range of contexts, including the fields of international development, healthcare, politics and employment. Health related QOL (HRQOL) is an evaluation of QOL and its relationship with health edition 20; [(1993),(cited on 2023 Dec 20)].
9. Kasvis P, Vigano M, Vigano A. Health-related quality of life across cancer cachexia stages. *Ann Palliat Med*;[(2019 Jan 8),(cited on 2023 Dec 17)];33-42.

10. Volk RJ, Cantor SB, Steinbauer JR, Alcohol use disorders, consumption patterns, and health-related quality of life of primary care patients. National Center for biotechnology information. [(1997 August), (2023 December13)]:899-905. Available from: <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9267541/>.
11. "UNICEF – Search Results". *unicef.org*. Retrieved 2015-10-20.
12. Cortina, M.A., Kahn, K., Fazel, M., Hlungwani, T., School based interventions can play a critical role in enhancing children's development and health in the developing world. National Center for Biotechnology information; Child Care, [(2008 January),(2023 December)]: 34(1), 1-3.
13. Kazem Akbari, Mahmood Rahmati. The effect of life skills training on the social communication of clients referring to drug abuse clinics. Jundishapcer Journal of chronic diseases care in press; [(2017 October), (2023 December 14)]: Available from: <https://www.researchgetnet/publication/322067531-The-Effect-of-Life-skills-Training-on-clients-Referring-to-Drug-Abuse-Clinics>.
14. Rajasenani Nair. Life skills for personality and leadership. Indian Council of Social Science research [(2010), (2023December 15)]
15. Pearlman R, Uhlmann R. Patient and physician perceptions of patient quality of life across chronic diseases. J Gerontol 1988;43: 25-30.
16. Lahmek P, Berlin I, Michel L, Berghout C, Meunier N & Aubin J H. Determinants of improvement in quality of life of alcohol-dependent patients during an inpatient withdrawal program Int J Med Sci. [(2009) (cited on 2023 Dec 16): 160-167.
17. Peltzer K, Pengpid S. Alcohol use and health related quality of life among hospital outpatients in South Africa. [(2012) (cited on 2023 Dec 17);47(3):291-5.
18. Sedslund G, Berg RC. Motivational interviewing for substance abuse. National center for biotechnology information; [(2011 May 11), (2023 December 16)]:1-126.
19. Angela H Jackson, Alford DP. Internal medicine residency training for unhealthy alcohol and other drug use. National library of medicine;[(online 2010 Mar 15), (cited on 2023 Dec 21)].
20. Toomey. Strategies to prevent under age drinking. National Library of Medicine;[(2002),(cited on 2023 Dec 17)]:26(1).5-14. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6683805>.
21. Chung T, Maisto S.A. Relapse to alcohol and other drug use in treated adolescents. Review and reconsideration of relapse as a change point in clinical course, clinical psychology review volume.26;[(2006),(cited on 2023Dec 18)];149-161.

22. Cox WM. The efficacy of motivational interviewing as a brief intervention for excessive drinking. National Library of Medicine. [(2006 Mar 17),(cited on 2023Dec 21)]:328-335.
23. Jagpreet kaur, VP Joshith. A life skills intervention aimed at changing attitudes of Indian youth towards alcohol and drugs abuse. Sri Lanka journal of psychiatry; [(2022 June), (cited on 2023 Dec17)]:13(1):42.
24. Effect of Life Skills Training on drug abuse preventive behaviors among university students. International journal of preventive medicine; [(online 2014 May 05),(cited on 2023 Dec14)]:577-583.
25. John F Kelly, Maricaferri. Alcoholics Anonymous and other 12-steps programs for alcohol use disorder. National center for Biotechnology information; [(online 2020 March 11), (cited on 2023 Dec18)]:3(3).
26. Shrvti Srivastava, Nanjeets. Bhatia. Quality of life as an outcome measure in the treatment of alcohol dependence industrial psychiatry journal; [(online 2013 January-June), (cited on 2023 Dec 20)]:41-46.
27. Hui Huang, Kui Ning. Quality of life and its correlates in Alcohol use Disorder Patients with and without Depression in China. National center for Biotechnology Information; [(online 2021 January 22), (cited on 2023 Dec18)].
28. Jeby Jose Olickal, Ganesh Kumar Saya. Association of alcohol use with quality of life a community based study from Puducherry, India. Clinical epidemiology and global health; [(online 2021 January), (cited on 2023 Dec16)]:10(10152).
29. Kishore Kumar Rai, Vandana. Role of life skills and attitude toward alcohol abuse in predicting academic achievement of school students. National center for Biotechnology Information; [(online 2022 November 26), (cited on 2023 Dec23)].
30. Rosbni, Rohit Kumar Turi. Application of Quality of life, problem solving skills and Treatment Motivation through Motivational Enhancement Therapy among Individuals journal of Indian psychology; [(online 2023 September 30), (cited on 2023 Dec 20)]:11(3).
31. Hanan Abd Elwabad, Rasmia Abd, Faten Mohamed Abmed. The effect of life skill intervention on social self efficacy for prevention of drug abuse among young adulterant students at Benba city. American journal of Nursing science; [(online 2019 September), (cited on 2023 Dec 15)]:8(5).
32. Basavanthappa B.T. Nursing Research. First edition. New Delhi: Jaypee Brothers, Medical Publishers. [(2000) (cited on 2023 Dec 20)]:158-160.